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NEWS

Visual Astronomy Display: December 2014

Katie Frey Updated on August 24, 2022 [Leave a Comment](#)

Visual Astronomy Display for December 2014

Highlights...

- NASA scientists Holly Gilbert and Alex Young talk about a **sunspot larger than any seen in the last 24 years** currently found on our star;
- After ten long years journeying through space, **Philae finally touches down onto the surface of a comet!**;
- Coming up in December is the **first test launch of Orion**, NASA's newest spacecraft designed to send humans farther into space than ever before;
- Tis the season for auroras! The **northern lights are on display** in several videos this month;
- AsapSCIENCE describes what it would take for people to begin **living on the Red Planet**; and
- Launched into space in 1999, the **Chandra X-Ray Observatory has helped revolutionize our understanding of the universe** through its unrivaled X-ray vision. Join NASA as they celebrate 15 years of amazing X-ray science!!

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Katie Frey leads the development of the Unified Astronomy Thesaurus, a community supported linked data vocabulary for sorting, filtering, and exploring astronomical literature, data sets, images, etc.

About Katie Frey

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